

Table S1. Locations and biological information for historic and contemporary oceanic sightings of North American bats.

Map ID	Date	Time	Species	Method	Coordinates	Georeference accuracy	Distance from land	Water depth (m)	Number	Sex	Height	Behavior	Weather	Source ^a
1	9/1/1890		silver-haired bat	Collection	40.95046, -69.432571	estimate	56.0	24	1					NMNH #23604
2	9/1/1890		eastern red bat	Collection	40.95046, -69.432571	estimate	56.0	24	1					NMNH #23605
3	first week of Sept, 1902	"night"	not specified	Sighting	37.552099, -76.178499	estimate	11.9	11	"a large migration"			"attempts to alight", "captured on the deck"		Allen 1923
4	first week of Sept, 1902	"night"	not specified	Sighting	39.124307, -75.225952	estimate	11.0	8	"a smaller visitation"					Allen 1923
5	9/6/1907		unknown, "little doubt they were Silver-hairs"	Sighting	40.474917, -73.90645	estimate	9.4	16	"a number"		"about a gun-shot above the sea"	"struggling toward the Staten Island shore"	"east wind was blowing", "heavy storm clouds hung low on the horizon", "choppy water", "gray, blustery morning"	Murphy and Nichols 1913
6	8/20/1913		silver-haired bat	Collection	42.552633, -70.660838	estimate	2.6	47	1	male		"caught with a crab net"		MCZ #14874
7	9/7/1918		silver-haired bat	Collection	40.687628, -72.864876	estimate	4.2	22	1	male				AMNH #182655
-	9/1/1920		eastern red bat	Sighting	unknown "3 days out from Philadelphia on our voyage from Cape Town, South Africa"				1			"clinging to the ledge under...giraffe box"		Haagren 1921
8	9/3/1919	7:07	eastern red bat	Sighting	36.970199, -74.856064	estimate	94.9	54	1			"darting about ship in erratic fashion, looking for cover", "settled between two booms on the fore-castle"	"clear, with a north-west breeze, rather light"	Nichols 1920
9	9/3/1920		eastern red and silver-haired bats	Collection	35.424689, -75.136965	estimate	31.5	29	"a flock of about a hundred"			"settled on ship", "migrating in a considerable flock"		Thomas 1921
10	8/17/1929		eastern red bat	Collection	42, -66	actual	161.8	98	1	male		"flew aboard...and rested on the main sail"	"no offshore gales have been reported from the region"	Norton 1930
11	8/18/1929		unknown	Collection	42.117615, -70.257639	estimate	6.4	60	1			"boarded"		MacCoy 1930
12	9/7/1937		unknown	Sighting	45.116667, -42.6	actual	817.3	4747	1		"within 15 or 20 feet"			Griffin 1940
13	8/25/1938		silver-haired bats	Sighting	39.15, -70.366667	actual	235.0	2758	3			"flying about the ship", "some remained on board searching dark places up to the time the ship reached the port"	"overcast with some rain and the wind was west-northwest at 20 miles per hour"	Carter 1950
14	9/29/1949	"day break"	eastern red bats	Collection	40.166667, -71	actual	123.7	137	"estimated at about 200"					
15	10/7/1952		eastern red bat	Collection	42.7, -62.966667	actual	196.9	1402	1	female			"may have been driven out to sea by strong winds"	Brown 1953
16	8/19/1953	11:00	silver-haired bat	Collection	39.6, -71.05	actual	176.2	2317	1	male		"circled the ship several times before coming to rest"	"light and variable 5-10 knot NW winds"	Mackiewicz and Backus 1956
17	8/25/1953	11:00	eastern red bat	Collection	39.633333, -70.316667	actual	180.7	2203	1	male		"captured in the rigging after...brief flight around the vessel"	"WNW winds of 5-10 knots prevailed"	Mackiewicz and Backus 1956
18	9/12/1962	12:00	eastern red bat	Collection	42.25, -67.516667	actual	201.6	260	1	female				MCZ #50177
19	9/24/1964	-	eastern red bat	Collection	36.2, -75.35	actual	33.6	31	1	-				AMNH #208650
20	mid-October, 1969	"early morning"	eastern red bat	Collection	42.5, -66.166667	actual	111.9	227	1	female				Peterson 1970
21	"over 2 days in late July or early August 2003"	"an hour before dusk"	Myotis, probably lucifugus	Sighting	"Gulf of Maine, about 1-10 km sw of a feature known as Southwest Bank"	estimate	69.8	160	"dozens"			"dozens circled about" "landed on author" "dozens hanging in rigging, wheelhouse, and living quarters" "near daylight everywhere on vessel by the dozens" "also roosting in high flier (large buoys) within 2-8 km" "by nightfall had dispersed"	"clear with warm temperatures and no wind" "no storms in area" "maximum wind speed was 12.2 km/hr with only 4 hourly records of >10km/hr winds"	Thompson et al. 2015
22	11/27 - 12/2/2010		eastern red bat	Sighting	43.89, -60.2	actual	163	31	3			"For 2-to-3 consecutive evenings, up to 3 bats were observed at dusk"	"mainly overcast, good visibility (18 km), temperature 5 to 8°C...predominantly northwest winds...Beaufort 2-6"	Czenze et al. 2011
23	9/6/2012	9:33	eastern red bat	Sighting	38.768562, -74.48744	actual	39.5		1		"within normal line of sight"	"flying southeast at a distance of approximately 150 m from the ship"	8.9 m/s from SW	Hatch et al. 2013
24	9/11/2012	7:56	eastern red bat	Video	38.741295, -74.801508	actual	23.6	16	1		>200 m	flying SW	9.3 m/s from NW	Hatch et al. 2013
25	9/11/2012	8:16	eastern red bat	Video	38.715514, -74.809183	actual	22.7	15	1			flying SW	9.3 m/s from NW	Hatch et al. 2013
26	9/11/2012	8:19	eastern red bat	Video	38.693065, -74.666917	actual	34.6	22	1			flying SW	9.3 m/s from NW	Hatch et al. 2013
27	9/11/2012	8:20	eastern red bat	Video	38.684703, -74.615381	actual	37.9	25	1			flying SW	9.3 m/s from NW	Hatch et al. 2013
28	9/11/2012	8:49	eastern red bat	Video	36.808896, -75.648807	actual	26.5	21	1			flying W	9.3 m/s from NW	Hatch et al. 2013
29	9/11/2012	9:41	eastern red bat	Video	37.014651, -75.451316	actual	44.6	27	1		>200 m	flying SW	10.1 m/s from N	Hatch et al. 2013
30	9/11/2012	9:43	eastern red bat	Video	37.027304, -75.517269	actual	38.7	22	1		>200 m	flying SW	10.1 m/s from N	Hatch et al. 2013
31	9/11/2012	9:45	eastern red bat	Video	37.055766, -75.63717	actual	27.6	16	1		100-200 m	flying SW	10.1 m/s from N	Hatch et al. 2013
32	9/11/2012	10:13	eastern red bat	Video	37.144471, -75.327618	actual	50.3	30	1		>200 m	flying SW	10.1 m/s from N	Hatch et al. 2013
33	9/11/2012	10:19	eastern red bat	Video	37.237921, -75.592406	actual	25.8	17	1		>200 m	flying SW	10.1 m/s from N	Hatch et al. 2013
34	9/11/2012	10:39	eastern red bat	Video	38.517294, -74.663008	actual	33.6	19	1			flying NW	10.1 m/s from N	Hatch et al. 2013
35	8/25/2017	10:30	eastern red bat	Photograph	41.698298, -69.749989	actual	15.4	62	1	female		"landed on boat" "stayed on boat all day and still on boat when it returned in the evening" "gone in the morning"		B. Perkins and D. O'Dell, pers comm.

36	10/19/2019		eastern red bat	Photograph	"35 nm from Hatteras, se from the inlet, in the Gulf Stream"	estimate	63.7	729	1	female	"flew onto captain's sweatshirt and landed on his arm" "took to shore under care of a vet and was released the next day"		K. Sutherland, pers comm.
37	10/10/2020	10:30	<i>Lasiurus</i> sp.	Photograph	36.848611, -74.7	actual	109.1	87	1	~9 m	"circled boat twice, then buzzed very closely before flying towards shore"	"wind blowing from southwest at 10-13 mph"	A. Rabon and J. B. Thornton, pers comm.

^a NMNH = Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History; MCZ = Museum of Comparative Zoology; AMNH = American Museum of Natural History